

WASTE SILK/WOOL HYBRID BIOCOMPOSITES WITH PBS MATRIX: PROCESSING, PROPERTIES AND E-BEAM TREATMENT EFFECT

Donghwan Cho* and Hwi Yong Lee

Department of Polymer Science and Engineering
Kumoh National Institute of Technology, Gumi, Gyeongbuk 730-701, South Korea

*Email: dcho@kumoh.ac.kr

Keywords: Hybrid biocomposites, Poly(butylene succinate), Waste silk/wool fibres, Properties

ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study are to produce hybrid biocomposites consisting of waste silk and waste wool as reinforcement and poly(butylene succinate) as matrix by using extrusion and injection processing technique and also to investigate the effect of E-beam treatment of the waste fibres on the thermal stability, thermo-dimensional stability, and dynamic mechanical, tensile, flexural, and impact, properties of the biocomposites. The study reveals that the mechanical and thermal properties depend on the electron beam absorption dose. The results indicate that the thermal and mechanical properties of the waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposite were increased with the E-beam treatment, most effectively at 10 kGy. This may be due to the enhanced interfacial adhesion between the waste fibres and the PBS matrix of the biocomposite through the surface treatment of the reinforcing waste fibres at an appropriate E-beam dose

1 INTRODUCTION

Industries and academia, which have been dealing with fibre-reinforced polymer composites, have been seeking for environmentally-benign composite materials. Natural fibre-reinforced biocomposites are environmentally friendly, less expensive, biodegradable, and easily processible. So far, plant-based natural fibre-reinforced biocomposites were studied a lot. Animal-based or protein-based natural fibres such as commercially available silk and wool have good mechanical properties [1,2]. Raw worm silk fibres (*Bombyx mori*), which can be commercially obtained from silkworm cocoons, consist of silk fibroin (75-83%) in the internal part and sericin (17-25%), waxes (1-2%), and other minor components in the external part [3]. In general, wool is less expensive than silk. Wool fibres with scale-shaped surfaces exhibit lower thermal stability and mechanical properties than silk fibre so that it is often commercially used with silk as mixed yarn. Also both waste silk and wool have potential as reinforcing fibre for composite materials [4,5].

Waste silk and wool are also industrially available with costless scrap fibres from relevant textile industries. Such natural fibres may be useful as environmentally-friendly, recyclable reinforcement for a fibre/polymer composite material. The waste fibres have good properties due to their good crystalline structure, the density is low, and the processibility for fabricating a composite is acceptable.

In our earlier studies, short worm silk fibre-reinforced PBS matrix biocomposites were prepared by using a compression moulding method and it was found that their mechanical and thermal properties significantly depend not only on the worm silk fibre content but also on the fibre length [1,6]. The sericin component can be removed from raw worm silk by a degumming process. It has been known that the silk fibroin fibre exhibits higher mechanical properties than worm silk fibres with the sericin due to the crystalline character of the fibroin component.

Biodegradable poly(butylene succinate) (simply referred to as PBS), which is one of the most promising biodegradable polymer resins, exhibits good processibility, versatile properties, and applications [7]. Recently, PBS has been increasingly studied as alternative of a synthetic polyethylene. PBS may often be subject to thermal and mechanical environments. In general, it has inferior thermal and mechanical properties in use. Therefore, it would be desirable if the thermal and mechanical properties of PBS can be improved.

Electron beam processing is a dry, clean and cold method with advantages such as energy-saving, high throughput rate, uniform irradiation and environmental safety. Electron beam technique has often been utilized for surface modification and property improvement of polymer materials like fibres, films, plastics and composites for the last decades [8]. It can remove surface impurities and alter surface characteristics at an appropriate irradiation condition. Cho *et al.* have reported a number of papers [9-12] demonstrating positive effects of natural fibre surface treatment on the interfacial properties of green composites as well as on the thermal and mechanical properties, particularly focusing on the electron beam irradiation of natural fibers on the properties of cellulose-based natural fibre biocomposites. In the case of cellulose-based natural fibers, it has been found that there exists an optimal electron beam intensity to effectively increase the interfacial adhesion as well as the thermal and mechanical properties. The positive effect gave rise to our research motivation on extending electron beam technology to animal-based natural fibres, in particular silk [4,13].

The objective of this study is to investigate how a hybrid type of natural fibre consisting of waste silk and wool influences the tensile, flexural, impact, thermo-dimensional stability, and thermal stability of biocomposites, produced by using extrusion and injection processing technique.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

In the present work, animal-based waste natural fibres consisting of silk fibroin and wool were used as reinforcing fibres for making random-type hybrid biocomposites. The mixing ratio of silk fibroin to wool was 4:6 and the average length of the individual waste fibres was in the range of 50-100 mm. PBS pellets (Model G4560-J) used were supplied from S-EnPol Inc., Korea. According to the manufacturer's information, the glass transition temperature is about -35°C, the crystallization temperature is in the range of 90~100°C, and the melting temperature is about 115°C. The neat PBS pellets and waste fibres were dried at 80°C for 4 hours in a convection oven in order to avoid possible moisture absorption prior to processing.

2.2 Processing of waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites

A modular intermeshing co-rotating twin-screw extruder (BT-30-S2-421, LG Machine Co., Korea) with the screw diameter of 30 mm and the L/D ratio of 42 was used for compounding neat PBS pellets with the mixed waste fibres. And then injection moulding process (Model PRO-WD 80, Donshin Hydraulic Co., Korea) was carried out for producing waste silk/wool fibre reinforced PBS hybrid biocomposites. Three kneading disc block configurations were used for efficient compounding of neat PBS with waste natural fibres. The hybrid biocomposites with the waste natural fibres irradiated by electron beam at various doses of 1, 5, 10, 30, and 50 kGy were also prepared by the same extrusion and injection processes. In this case, the waste fibre/PBS ratio was fixed to 30/70 by weight. The specimens to be used for tensile, flexural, impact and dynamic mechanical tests were directly obtained by the injection moulding.

2.3 Electron beam treatment of waste fibres

Electron beam (E-beam) treatment of waste silk/wool fibres was carried out at ambient temperature in air using an E-beam apparatus (ELV-8, EB Tech Co., Korea). The E-beam processes were performed with the E-beam energy of 0.57 MeV, the current of 2.88 mA, and the conveying speed of 20 m/min for 1 and 5 kGy and with the E-energy of 1.14 MeV, the current of 7.2 mA, and the conveying speed of 10 m/min for 10, 30, and 50 kGy. The dose was controlled by counting the rotation number of the conveyor cart passing through the channel equipped with the E-beam irradiation facility in the middle of the channel.

2.4 Thermal analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA Q500, TA Instruments, USA) was performed to 600°C in order to investigate the thermal stability and degradation behaviour of the biocomposites. The heating rate of

10°C/min was used with the sample of 8~10 mg purging a nitrogen gas. An alumina pan was used. Derivative thermogravimetry (DTG) curves were also obtained to examine the weight loss rate as a function of temperature.

Thermomechanical analysis (TMA 2940, TA Instruments, USA) was carried out to 100°C with the heating rate of 10°C/min purging a nitrogen gas to examine the thermal expansion behaviour of the biocomposites. A macro-expansion mode was used throughout the TMA measurement. The specimen dimensions were 5 mm × 5 mm × 3 mm.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA, Q800, TA Instruments, USA) was used to explore the dynamic mechanical properties. The specimen dimensions were 63.5 mm × 12.5 mm × 3 mm. A dual cantilever mode was applied throughout the DMA measurement. Each DMA measurement was performed from -60°C to 100°C with the heating rate of 2°C/min, purging a liquid nitrogen gas. The oscillation amplitude was 0.1 mm and the sinusoidally oscillating frequency was 1 Hz.

2.5 Mechanical testing

Tensile testing of the injection-moulded biocomposites was performed at ambient temperature using a universal testing machine (UTM, Shimadzu JP/AG-50kNX, Japan) according to the ASTM D 638M standard. The load cell used was 5 kN and the crosshead speed was 50 mm/min. The dog-bone type specimens were used. The average values of the tensile strength and tensile modulus were obtained from ten specimens.

Three-point flexural testing for the injection-moulded biocomposites was performed at ambient temperature using a universal testing machine (UTM, Shimadzu JP/AG-50kNX, Japan) according to the ASTM D790M standard. The span-to-depth ratio was 32:1. The load cell used was 50 kN and the crosshead speed was 5.1 mm/min. The average values of the flexural strength and modulus were obtained from ten specimens.

Izod impact tests of the injection-moulded biocomposites were carried out at ambient temperature according to the ASTM D256 standard by using a pendulum-type impact tester (Tinius Olsen, Model 892, UK). Each specimen has the dimensions of 65 mm × 12.5 mm × 3 mm with 'V'-shaped notch (2.5 mm in depth) made by using a notch cutter according to the ASTM D256. The test was performed at an impact rate of the pendulum of 3.46 m/s. The impact distance was 610 mm and the impact energy was 12.66 J. The average impact strength was obtained from ten specimens.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal stability

Figure 1 shows the TGA and DTG curves measured with waste silk fibroin fibre, waste wool fibre, neat PBS and various hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres irradiated at different doses. The DTG curves provide useful information on the component and the mutual effect of the components in a composite. It was found that the waste fibres show the fast weight loss at about 300°C. The biocomposites exhibited the roughly intermediate thermal stability between the waste fibres and the neat PBS. It is obvious that the thermal stability of the biocomposites below about 370°C was lower than that of neat PBS but higher than that of the two waste fibres. This is because the biocomposites consist of 70 wt% PBS matrix, which exhibits higher thermal stability than the waste fibres. The higher residual weight in the biocomposite than neat PBS was due to the greater residual weight of the silk and wool fibres than PBS at above 370°C. The DTG curves show two distinguishable peaks. The primary peak occurred at about 315°C was due to the weight loss resulting from the thermal degradation of the silk fibroin and wool fibres and the secondary peak at about 385°C was due mainly to the thermal degradation of PBS in the biocomposite. The silk fibroin and wool fibres showed the initial weight loss from about 50°C even after drying. The thermal stability of the waste silk fibroin is higher than that of the waste wool in the whole temperature range. The considerable weight loss of the waste wool occurred at about 200°C. In both the waste fibres, the weight loss started at about 200°C. The curves reveal that the biocomposites have a similar fibre/matrix ratio. The result also reveals that the electron beam treatment done to the waste fibres did not affect significantly the thermal stability of the biocomposites.

Figure 1: TGA (A) and DTG (B) curves for waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at various electron beam absorption doses.

3.2 Thermal expansion behaviour

Table 1 compares the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at different E-beam absorption doses. The CTE values were determined from the slope of the TMA curve in the range of 40~60°C and 60~80°C, respectively. The thermal expansion of the biocomposites was considerably lower than that of neat PBS due to the presence of the waste fibres. In most cases, the thermal expansion of treated waste fibre/PBS biocomposites was less than that of un-treated one. The lowest CTE value was obtained at 10-30 kGy, reflecting the greatest thermo-dimensional stability. The highest expansion was occurred at 1 kGy. E-beam treatment contributed to enhancing the thermo-dimensional stability due to the removal of surface impurities existing in the waste fibres. It is mentioned that incorporating the waste fibres into the neat PBS enhances the thermo-dimensional stability of neat PBS and also treating the fibre surfaces with the E-beam between 10 and 30 kGy further decreases the thermal expansion of the hybrid biocomposites.

Waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites	CTE($10^{-4}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	
	(40°C~60°C)	(60°C~80°C)
0 kGy	1.44	1.77
1 kGy	1.38	1.84
5 kGy	1.29	1.63
10 kGy	1.23	1.50
30 kGy	1.22	1.58
50 kGy	0.87	1.28

Table 1: CTE values in different temperature regions for waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at various E-beam absorption doses.

3.3 Dynamic mechanical properties

Table 2 shows the variations of the storage modulus of the hybrid composites treated at different E-beam absorption doses. The treated waste fibre/PBS biocomposite exhibited much higher storage modulus than the untreated one. The highest storage modulus was obtained with the E-beam of 50 kGy at -30°C and with 10 kGy at 25°C. The result indicates that E-beam treatment done to the fibres contributed to enhancing the dynamic mechanical properties of the biocomposite. It is thought that the interfacial adhesion between the fibre and the matrix was increased by the surface treatment. Below

the glass transition region the E-beam lower than 10 kGy was too low to remove the surface impurities forming a weak boundary layer in the biocomposite. It is noted that the incorporation of the waste fibres to neat PBS played a role in reinforcing the PBS. As expected the storage modulus was markedly decreased above the glass transition region.

Waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites	Storage modulus (MPa)	
	at -30 °C	at 25 °C
0 kGy	2507	1167
1 kGy	2796	1318
5 kGy	2797	1337
10 kGy	2864	1453
30 kGy	2845	1414
50 kGy	2962	1360

Table 2: Storage moduli at -30 °C, and 25 °C of waste silk/wool/PBS biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at various E-beam absorption doses.

3.4 Tensile properties

Figure 2 shows the tensile strength and modulus of the hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at different absorption doses. Among the specimens, the biocomposite with the untreated waste fibres exhibited the lowest flexural strength and modulus. The biocomposite with the fibres treated at 10 kGy showed the maximum tensile properties. Both the tensile strength and modulus were increased with the E-beam treatment even at such a low energy of 1 kGy, further gradually increased with increasing the dose to 10 kGy and then decreased at 50 kGy. The result indicates that the E-beam treatment with an optimal dose at 10-30 kGy contributed to enhancing the tensile properties. It was noticeable that the tensile strength was increased with the incorporation of animal-based waste natural fibres. As reported in our earlier studies [9,10], an electron beam irradiation of 10 kGy was preferable for enhancing the mechanical properties of cellulose-based natural fibre reinforced biocomposites.

Figure 2: A comparison of tensile modulus (A), strength (B) of waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at various E-beam absorption doses.

3.5 Flexural properties

Figure 3 compares the flexural strength and modulus of the hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at different absorption doses. The untreated biocomposite exhibited the lowest flexural strength and modulus. The biocomposite treated at 10 kGy showed the maximum flexural properties. The E-beam treatment higher than 30 kGy rather decreased the strength and modulus. The result informs that the flexural properties by the E-beam treatment were somewhat increased when the treatment was carried out at the dose lower than 10 kGy or higher than 30 kGy. It is noticed that the

flexural strength was increased with the incorporation of the waste natural fibres, as similarly found from the tensile result.

Figure 3: A comparison of flexural modulus (A), strength (B) of waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at various E-beam absorption doses.

3.6 Impact property

Figure 4 depicts the effect of E-beam treatment on the Izod impact strength of the hybrid biocomposites. The impact strength of the biocomposite with the waste fibres untreated was highest. The impact strengths of the biocomposite with the waste fibres treated were lower than that of the untreated, depending on the E-beam absorption dose. The highly increased impact strength was obtained at 10 kGy, almost recovering the decreased impact strength. With increasing the dose, the impact strength was gradually increased up to 10 kGy, indicating that the interfacial adhesion between the waste fibres and the PBS matrix was best at 10 kGy. The initial decrease of the impact strength at 1 kGy indicates that such low E-beam energy is too low to remove the surface impurities. The remarkable decrease of the impact strength at 50 kGy may be due to possible damages of the waste fibre by such relatively high E-beam energy, as similarly found in the tensile and flexural results.

Figure 4: Impact strength for waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites with the waste fibres treated at various E-beam absorption doses.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of E-beam treatment of the waste fibres on the thermal and mechanical properties of waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposites produced by extrusion and injection moulding was studied and the following conclusions were obtained.

1. The thermal stability of the hybrid biocomposite was not significantly influenced by the E-beam treatment, whereas the treatment of the waste fibre surfaces with the E-beam between 10 and 30 kGy increased the thermo-dimensional stability of the biocomposites.

2. The E-beam treatment done to the waste fibres contributed to enhancing the dynamic mechanical properties of the biocomposite. It was obvious that the incorporation of the waste fibres into neat PBS played a significant role in reinforcing the PBS.

3. The result indicates that the E-beam treatment with an optimal dose at 10-30 kGy contributed to enhancing the tensile properties. Both the flexural strength and modulus increased with the E-beam treatment were effectively increased at 10 kGy with the maximum. Among the E-beam treated biocomposites, the impact strength exhibited the maximum at 10 kGy,

It is mentioned that the enhancement of the thermal, mechanical and impact properties of the waste silk/wool/PBS hybrid biocomposite may be explained by the increased interfacial adhesion between the waste fibres and the PBS matrix through the E-beam treatment and 10 kGy may be preferable for treating animal-based natural fibres with E-beam

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NSF) grant funded by the Korea Government (MSIP).

REFERENCES

- [1] S.M. Lee, D. Cho, W.H. Park, S.G. Lee, S.O. Han and L.T. Drzal, Novel silk/poly(butylene succinate) biocomposites: the effect of short fiber content on their mechanical and thermal properties”, *Composites Science and Technology*, **65**, 2005, pp. 647-657.
- [2] M.P. Ho, K.T. Lau, H. Wang and D. Bhattacharyya, Characteristics of a silk fibre reinforced biodegradable plastic, *Composites: Part B*, **42**, 2011, pp. 117-22.
- [3] Y. Kim, O.H. Kwon, W.H. Park and D. Cho, “Thermo-mechanical and Flexural Properties of Chopped Silk Fiber-reinforced Poly(butylene succinate) Green Composites: Effect of Electron Beam Treatment of Worm Silk”, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **22**, 2013, pp. 437-449.
- [4] S.O. Han, S.M. Lee, W.H. Park and D. Cho, Mechanical and thermal properties of waste silk fiber-reinforced poly(butylene succinate) biocomposites”, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **100**, 2006, pp. 4972-4980.
- [5] K.H. Kim, D. Cho and J. H. Kim, Fabrication and properties of natural fiber-reinforced waste wool/polypropylene composites (NFRP)”, *Journal of Adhesion and Interface*, **9**, 2008, pp. 16-23.
- [6] S.M. Lee, S.O. Han, D. Cho, W.H. Park and S.G. Lee, Influence of chopped fibre length on the mechanical and thermal properties of silk fibre-reinforced PBS biocomposites”, *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, **13**, 2005, pp. 479-488.
- [7] M. Suhartini, H. Mitomo, N. Nagasawa, F. Yoshii and T. Kume, Radiation crosslinking of poly(butylene succinate) in the presence of low concentrations of trimethyllyl isocyanurate and its properties, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **88**, **2003**, pp.2238-2246.
- [8] D. Cho, H.J. Kim and L.T. Drzal, *Polymer Composites Volume 3: Biocomposites*, Edited S. Thomas, K. Joseph, S.K. Malhotra, K. Goda and M.S. Sreekala, Wiley-VCH Verlag, Weinheim, pp. 133-177, 2013.
- [9] Y. Pang, D. Cho, S.O. Han and W.H. Park, Interfacial shear strength and thermal properties of electron beam-treated henequen fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester composites, *Macromolecular Research*, **13**, 2005, pp. 453-459.
- [10] S.O. Han, D. Cho, W.H. Park and L.T. Drzal, Henequen/poly(butylene succinate) biocomposites: electron beam irradiation effects on henequen fiber and the interfacial properties of biocomposites, *Composite Interfaces*, **13**, 2006, pp. 231-247.
- [11] D. Cho, H.S. Lee, S.O. Han and L.T. Drzal, “Effects of E-beam treatment on the interfacial and mechanical properties of henequen/polypropylene biocomposites, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **16**, 2007, pp. 315-334.
- [12] D. Cho, H.S. Lee and S.O. Han, Effect of fiber surface modification on the interfacial and mechanical properties of kenaf fiber-reinforced thermoplastic and thermosetting polymer composites, *Composite Interfaces*, **16**, 2009, pp. 711-729.

- [13] Y. Kim, D. Cho, W.H. Park and O.H. Kwon, Novel silk fibroin fiber-reinforced poly(butylene succinate) biocomposites: electron beam treatment effect of silk on the interfacial, thermal, mechanical and impact properties, *Journal of Biobased Materials and Bioenergy*, **8**, 2014, pp. 261-272.